

Scenario-Based Assessment as a Driver of the Lower Secondary School Competency-Based Curriculum in Uganda

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Abstract

Adopting a Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) marks a significant shift in educational paradigms, with scenario-based assessment emerging as a cornerstone of this evolution. Grounded in Constructivist Learning Theories, Situated Learning Theory, and Problem-Based Learning theory, scenario-based assessment immerses students in real-world situations, fostering active learning, critical thinking, and practical competence. Scholars highlight various forms of scenario-based assessment, including case studies, simulations, and problem-based scenarios, each offering unique benefits for evaluating students' abilities. Facilitating factors influencing scenario-based assessment include clear learning objectives, structured rubrics, collaborative learning environments, timely feedback, and technology integration. However, obstacles such as ambiguous learning objectives, examiner bias, inadequate feedback mechanisms, and resource limitations can hinder assessment outcomes. Addressing these challenges is essential to ensure the integrity and efficacy of scenario-based assessment in promoting deeper learning and preparing students for the complexities of the 21st century.

Keywords: *Competency-Based Curricula, scenario-based assessment, constructivist learning theories, situated learning theory, problem-based learning theory, critical thinking, problem-solving, facilitators, inhibitors, education.*

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Introduction

A significant revolution is underway as nations embrace Competency-Based Curricula (CBC), moving away from traditional content-centered methodologies toward dynamic, student-centered models. As students across all regions in Uganda prepare for their final summative assessment within the CBC framework, the main evaluation tool in view is the novel scenario-based assessment. Based on constructivist learning theories, this innovative approach immerses students in actual and plausible settings, challenging them to apply their competencies and abilities to face real-world situations. By effectively implementing active learning, critical thinking, and meaningful engagement during the regular learning processes, scenario-based assessment emerges cornerstone in educational assessment evolution, promising to provide learners globally with the diverse competencies required to navigate the difficulties of the 21st century.

Several scholars (e.g., Jonassen et al., 1999) have posited their insights about scenario-based assessment, which involves providing students with "a narrative of a real or realistic situation, with information and conditions that permit the student to make a decision or solve a problem" (Darabi, Arrastia, Nelson, Cornille, & Liang, 2011). According to Darabi et al., this approach highlights the need for the genuine nature of scenarios and their function in enhancing decision-making and problem-solving abilities. By engaging with realistic scenarios, students can develop their critical thinking skills and get valuable experience in navigating challenging situations by applying theoretical information to real-life contexts. According to Haynes et al. (2009) cited in (Mutweleli, Mwathe, & Mundi, 2024), scenario-based assessment is a significant breakthrough in educational evaluation as it emphasizes the application of knowledge and skills in actual, real-world situations. Unlike traditional content-based assessments, which primarily focus on remembering facts and figures, scenario-based assessments put students in realistic circumstances where they must demonstrate their ability to analyze, synthesize, and apply their knowledge to solve complex problems or make informed decisions. The scenario-based assessment presents students with realistic scenarios or case studies that mirror situations they may encounter in their future academic or professional lives. These may require them to draw upon multiple disciplines and competencies to devise solutions or responses using the acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies to analyze the problem, discover important facts, and provide possible solutions or actions. This strategy promotes deeper learning and makes it easier to apply whatever students have learnt in real-world settings.

Banerjee (2019) observes that while traditional content-based assessments are primarily concerned with recalling factual information, scenario-based assessments emphasize the application and synthesis of knowledge within contextualized scenarios. Although both assessment systems seek to examine students' comprehension of information, scenario-based assessment takes a step further by examining students' ability to apply their knowledge in real-world circumstances and it focuses on higher-order thinking skills, problem-solving ability, and real-world application. According to Banerjee, traditional assessments often use conventional tests or exams with predetermined questions, but scenario-based assessments offer greater versatility and originality in assessment design.

In the context of CBC, scenario-based assessment is well aligned with the curriculum's goals of building a variety of competencies necessary for overall student growth as it promotes deeper learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities by immersing students in realistic circumstances that require the application of previously acquired knowledge and skills. In addition, it builds transferable skills like adaptability, creativity, cooperation, and resilience, which are highly appreciated in today's dynamic workforce and these prepare students to handle challenging real-world situations, providing them with the skills and abilities required to flourish in an ever-changing educational, professional, and societal setting (Guerrero-Roldán & Noguera, 2018).

Taras (2016, p.846) observes that scenario-based assessment is "an assessment tool that requires a student to construct responses based on realistic situations or scenarios", emphasizing the importance of students actively developing responses rather than passively retaining facts. Taras pointed out different forms of scenario-based assessment which can offer diverse techniques for educators to assess students' ability to apply their understanding in meaningful contexts, developing deeper comprehension, critical thinking, and practical competence across a variety of subjects and domains. These include case study assessment, problem-based scenario, performance task assessment, and decision-making assessment (Taras, 2016).

Case study assessments provide students with extensive descriptions of actual or simulated situations, which are frequently drawn from professional contexts or historical events. In a case study assessment, students are asked to analyze the case, identify important concerns, and propose solutions or recommendations based on their knowledge of pertinent concepts and principles in the scenario (Schuwirth & Van der Vleuten, 2003). Simulation assessments are interactive and dynamic settings that mimic real-world circumstances or systems. Students can be made to participate in role-playing exercises, virtual simulations, or computer-based simulations during assessment in which they must make decisions, conduct actions, and see the effects of their choices in a simulated environment (Marshall et al., 2015). Problem-based scenario assessment offers students an opportunity to utilize their knowledge and skills to solve specific problems or tasks. These situations may require students to identify the root causes of an issue, brainstorm potential remedies, and assess the efficacy of various approaches (Segers, Dochy, & De Corte, 1999). Performance task assessment involves assessing students as they participate in real, hands-on activities that challenge them to apply their knowledge and abilities to complete a task or create a product. Examples of performance task assessment include developing a solution to a real-world problem, carrying out tasks or research, and generating multimedia presentations (Palm, 2019). The use of performance-based assessment methods such as presentations, simulations, role-playing, projects, or problem-solving assignments in scenario-based situations enables a more comprehensive examination of students'

abilities such as critical thinking, decision-making, communication, and teamwork than just memory (Haynes, Spence, & Lenze, 2009). Decision-making task within scenario-based assessment offers students an innovative and engaging opportunity to apply their knowledge, consider diverse perspectives, and develop practical decision-making skills in authentic scenarios. Students develop critical thinking skills by dealing with complex decision points and weighing multiple possibilities. These skills are necessary for success in both academic and real-world situations (Seren Smith, Warnes, & Vanhoestenbergh, 2018).

Uganda's education system embraces the principles of competency-based education and scenario-based assessment, ushering in a new era of student-centered learning and assessments; a journey that promises to empower students with the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to succeed in the 21st century and beyond. This conceptual review study has enlightened on the diverse forms of scenario-based assessments and the factors that may support or inhibit the outcomes of these assessments outcomes. The review also provides recommendations to stakeholders to guarantee its successful and efficient implementation.

Methodology

The study employed a narrative systematic literature review methodology to synthesize studies examining the variety of scenario-based assessments and the components that are likely to facilitate or hinder the outputs of these assessment results in Uganda's competency-based lower secondary school curriculum. Several indexing websites, including Research Gate, Academia.edu, Google Scholar, and Google, were used to gather the material. One of the inclusion criteria of a literature source for the review was the relevance of its content to scenarios-based assessment about formats and factors that facilitate or hinder the outcomes of such assessments globally. A minimal number of sources were used that contained assessment data besides scenario-based assessment. The relevant literature was examined based on the various researchers' comparisons and contrasts of their views. The review was broken down into sections that covered the introduction, methodology, theoretical framework, and factors that can either facilitates or hinders the results of scenario-based assessments in Uganda's competency-based lower secondary school curriculum. In the end, we offer conclusions and recommendations.

Theoretical Framework to Explore Facilitating and Inhibiting Factors Influencing Scenario-Based Assessment Results

Several nations worldwide have embarked on significant initiatives to enhance the quality of their educational systems to meet global demands, and Uganda is no exception. The country has embraced a Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), a process initiated by the National Curriculum Development Center in collaboration with the Ministry of Education and Sports. Rolled out in February 2020, the CBC aims to equip students with the essential skills and competencies needed for contemporary society. Moreover, the CBC aligns with the fourth Sustainable Development Goal, striving for inclusive, equitable, and quality education for all (Charles, Song, & Khaing, 2022). Within any educational system, assessment serves as a pivotal component in evaluating curriculum implementation quality. It informs instructional practices, monitors student progress, aids decision-making, evaluates outcomes, fosters

accountability, facilitates communication among stakeholders, and promotes equity and inclusion. Particularly in Uganda, the Uganda National Examination Board (UNEB), along with other stakeholders, is integrating scenario-based assessment. This assessment tool prompts students to construct responses grounded in realistic scenarios across various subjects (Resnick & Resnick, 1992).

In this conceptual study, we delve into the facilitating and inhibiting factors influencing scenario-based assessment results, considering the diversity of school-based factors. A theoretical understanding of such factors can be provided by Jean Piaget's constructivism theory (Utley, 2010), situated learning by Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger (Wenger, 2022), and Problem-Based Learning theory by Barrows and Tamblyn (Dolmans & Schmidt, 2010). Each of these is independently considered because of their potential impact on the student's scenario-based assessment results.

Constructivism Theory

The concepts of constructivism can greatly influence teaching and learning strategies in Uganda's lower secondary school competency-based curriculum, supporting the nation's educational objectives and challenges. Like many developing countries, Uganda confronts several challenges in delivering high-quality education, such as limited resources, substantial class sizes, and a diverse student body (Kidega, Song, Ugochinyere, James, & Ndikubwimana, 2024). Teachers in Uganda can modify their teaching strategies to better meet the needs of their students and create meaningful learning experiences by adopting the constructivist tenets.

Constructivism is a philosophy that believes knowledge cannot exist outside the mind (Murphy, 1997). Knowledge cannot be transferred from one mind to another. Individuals create new knowledge through their own experiences (Hendry, Frommer, & Walker, 1999). The key principle of this theory makes knowledge to be viewed as spatial and temporal patterns that emerge from people's interpretations and views of the environment. These interpretations are impacted by prior knowledge and are developed in conjunction with the environment. Despite differences in individuals' experiences and backgrounds, common knowledge and reasoning processes develop from shared perceptual information and behaviors. Knowledge formation entails perception, action, and the resolution of conceptual problems, which results in the emergence of new, durable forms of knowledge. This process takes mental effort and time, yet it is eventually enjoyable or fulfilling (Al-Huneidi & Schreurs, 2013). In line with the above theory, Learning can therefore be regarded as an active process by which students develop and re-attain long-term knowledge through perception, activity, and the resolution of conceptual problems. Learning is the process of developing new information and meaning through interactions with the world, such as engaging with instructional materials, and manipulating instruments sequentially in a coordinated and connected manner (Hyun, Ediger, & Lee, 2017). Therefore, enhancing students' ability to develop and re-attain long-term knowledge would include the following but not limited to; Encourage students' active participation and engagement in learning activities such as discussions, hands-on experiences, and problem-solving exercises. This enables students to build their comprehension through active participation rather than passive observation (Himmele & Himmele, 2017). Provide opportunities for interdisciplinary learning activities that bring together information from multiple fields and real-world situations. This builds links between different fields of knowledge and a comprehensive comprehension of topics and subjects (Klaassen, 2018). Incorporate experiential learning opportunities, such as internships, fieldwork, or simulations that allow students to apply their knowledge in

real-world contexts. This helps Students Bridge the gap between theory and practice and improves their ability to apply what they have learned in real-world circumstances (Aithal & Mishra, 2024). Encourage collaborative learning spaces in which students can engage in peer interactions, share perspectives, and co-create knowledge. Collaborating students learning promotes active debate, critical thinking, and the investigation of other perspectives (Mirijamdotter, Somerville, & Holst, 2006). Incorporate opportunities for reflection and metacognitive exercises into your learning process. Teachers should encourage students to think about their learning experiences, assess their comprehension, and recommend areas for deeper study or improvement. This fosters more profound understanding and self-directed learning skills (McAlpine, Weston, Beauchamp, Wiseman, & Beauchamp, 1999). Provide access to a variety of educational materials and techniques, such as multimedia materials, interactive simulations, and online platforms. This fits various learning methods and preferences while increasing engagement and comprehension (Smith & Casserly, 2006). When teachers regularly uses formative assessment procedures that offer continuous feedback and opportunity for self-evaluation and review, students can monitor their progress, identify areas for growth, and adapt their learning strategy accordingly and Create inclusive and supportive learning environments that identify and address students' different needs, backgrounds, and learning styles (Clark, 2012). Create an environment of respect, collaboration, and mutual support in which all students feel valued and empowered to actively engage in the learning process (Salend, 2010). Therefore, Learning practices can improve scenario-based assessment results by aligning them with the principles of active engagement, interdisciplinary connections, experiential learning, collaboration, reflection, metacognition, multimodal resources, formative assessment, and inclusive learning environments. These approaches encourage deeper comprehension, critical thinking, and meaningful learning experiences, resulting in better evaluation scores for students (Norris, Grohs, & Knight, 2022).

Situated Learning Theory

Situated Learning Theory provides important insights into how learning can be maximized in the Ugandan lower secondary school competency-based educational system by acknowledging the social and cultural diversity that exist (Kaweesi, Ayebare, Atibuni, & Olema, 2023). Originally introduced by Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger in the 1990s, this theory emphasizes that learning is a social process that takes place in communities of practice and real-world environments rather than in a vacuum (Wenger, 2022). This would therefore means for the best scenario-based assessment results to be realized in the lower secondary school competency-based curriculum, learning should be grounded in authentic practice contexts, where students engage in increasingly complex tasks within social networks (binti Pengiran & Besar, 2018). When teachers exposed students to authentic settings, they develop intrinsic social learning methods that involve them alongside more experienced persons, bringing deeper insights into real-world settings (Pitchford, Owen, & Stevens, 2020). Learning, social interaction, and real-world practice are all integrated in professional organizations. By emphasizing the importance of context, involvement, and cooperation, the theory gives light on how learning happens in real-world situations and how educational techniques can be adapted to produce meaningful and effective learning experiences (King, 2012).

In line with Situated Learning Theory, learning can be viewed as a social and contextual process where individuals engage in real activities within communities of practice,

collaborating with more experienced members to solve problems (Lave, 1991). Learning is more than just acquiring knowledge and skills; it is also about developing one's identity and competence within a particular context (Lave, 1991). Which can be further enhanced by; providing opportunity for students to participate in actual tasks and activities that represent real-world issues and situations relevant to their field of interest (Renzulli, Gentry, & Reis, 2021). This enables students to build practical skills and knowledge relevant to their eventual professional contexts, Encourage learners to participate in communities of practice, where they can communicate with peers and more experienced members, share expertise, and collaborate on learning activities. Encourage active participation in group discussions, collaborative problem-solving, and knowledge sharing to encourage deeper comprehension and skill development, facilitate learners' participation in the community of practice by allowing for legitimate peripheral participation. Allow students to gradually increase their degree of engagement and responsibility in the community, offering direction and support as they progress from periphery to full participation, incorporate authentic tasks, simulations, case studies, and field experiences to immerse students in meaningful learning activities that promote the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical application. Create learning environments that reflect real-world contexts and allow for hands-on, experiential learning, social interactions and teamwork are essential components of the learning process. Encourage learners to engage in discourse, peer feedback, and cooperative problem-solving, both in person and via online platforms, to aid in knowledge production and the formation of common understandings within the community of practice. Integrating situated learning theory concepts into normal instructional strategies can result in scenario-based assessments that are more relevant, authentic, and represent students' preparation for professional practice or real-world scenarios. Scenario-based assessment allows students to demonstrate their knowledge, skills, and competencies in relevant and applicable ways to their future careers or academic pursuits by providing opportunities for authentic performance, collaborative problem-solving, progressive development, contextualized understanding, and intellectual curiosity (Errington, 2010).

The Problem-Based Learning (PBL) Theory

In the context of Uganda's secondary school competency-based curriculum and scenario-based assessment results, Problem-Based Learning (PBL) Theory offers a valuable educational strategy that aligns with the country's goals of fostering meaningful and effective learning experiences. Developed by Howard Barrows and Sylvia Tamblyn, PBL emphasizes the use of authentic, ill-structured challenges as the starting point for learning (Krenik, 2014). According to this method, learning is more effective when it takes place in the context of solving real-world problems as opposed to using conventional teacher-centered techniques. (Krenik, 2014). This approach highlights the role of authentic challenges, student-centered learning, engagement, interdisciplinary connections, self-directed learning, collaborative learning, and reflection in fostering meaningful and effective learning experiences (Singh, 2011). Using PBL principles, educators can build dynamic learning environments that enable students to develop critical skills and competencies for success in the 21st century (Afandi, 2023).

Factors Facilitating Scenario-Based Assessment Results

Scenario-based assessment is a dynamic method particularly relevant within Uganda's lower secondary school competency-based curriculum. As this curriculum aims to equip students with practical skills and competencies for real-world application, scenario-based assessment becomes a valuable tool for evaluating students' readiness to tackle authentic challenges. By exposing students to real-world scenarios requiring critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making, this assessment method closely aligns with the curriculum's objectives. It allows educators to assess not only students' theoretical knowledge but also their ability to apply that knowledge practically. Through scenario-based assessment, students engage in active learning experiences simulating real-world challenges, fostering deeper understanding and retention of concepts. This approach promotes student engagement and relevance by enabling them to apply their knowledge in contexts mirroring future academic or professional challenges. Overall, scenario-based assessment provides a valuable framework for evaluating students' readiness to apply knowledge and skills in real-world situations, an essential component of Uganda's lower secondary school competency-based curriculum. (Norris et al., 2022). Several scholars have pointed out accelerating factors for effective scenario-based assessment results, which are not limited to the following:

Real-world scenarios that are closely connected with authentic scenarios foster student engagement and relevance by enabling them to apply their knowledge and abilities in relevant contexts. Teachers should create carefully thought-out scenario items that reflect real-world or professional challenges in order to promote deeper learning and more accurate assessment outcomes (Berry, 2008).

Well-defined learning objectives facilitate students' comprehension of expectations and direct their interaction with the scenario. Subject matter experts should make sure students are aware of the expected learning outcomes in each chapter. This is because students can concentrate their efforts on demonstrating the required knowledge, skills, and competencies when they are aware of the assessment goals, which results in more successful assessment outcomes (Demetriadis, Papadopoulos, Stamelos, & Fischer, 2008).

Scenario-based test items with structured rubrics give clear standards for judging student performance and provide detailed comments on their answers. By providing precise expectations and success criteria, these rubrics are essential in helping item developers and students alike comprehend assessment criteria and intended results. Structured rubrics guarantee uniformity and impartiality in evaluation by decomposing difficult assessment tasks into manageable parts. This enables item developers to give focused feedback that promotes student growth and learning. Additionally, they encourage responsibility and openness in the evaluation procedure, cultivating a mutual comprehension of anticipated outcomes and enabling significant introspection on accomplishments. All things considered, structured rubrics improve the validity, efficacy, and reliability of scenario-based assessment items, producing assessment findings that are more precise and instructive (Zhang, van Rijn, Deane, & Bennett, 2019). In addition to providing greater engagement with the scenario and facilitating the sharing of ideas and viewpoints, collaborative learning settings expose students to a variety of real-world circumstances through peer interaction, discussion, and cooperation. Collaborative problem-solving improves communication, critical thinking, teamwork, and knowledge retention, which produces more thorough assessment outcomes (Barkley, Major, & Cross, 2014).

Timely and constructive feedback directs students' learning and encourages performance reflection by assisting them in understanding their areas of strength and growth. When using scenario-based assessment, educators should give prompt and helpful feedback. Enhancing students' metacognitive awareness and leading to more successful assessment results is achieved by encouraging them to reflect on their experiences, pinpoint areas for growth, and create goals for their future education (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006). Support and direction from the instructor are crucial for enabling successful scenario-based assessment outcomes. Clear directions, learning activity scaffolding, and encouragement and instruction during the evaluation process all assist students in navigating the situation and advancing their comprehension and abilities. Clarifying expectations, clearing up misunderstandings, and improving student performance are all possible with the help of instructor feedback and direction (Bardach et al., 2021).

By offering interactive simulations, multimedia resources, and online platforms for collaboration and communication, the integration of technology tools and resources can improve the efficacy of scenario-based assessment. Realistic, immersive experiences and more dynamic, interactive assessment activities are made possible by technologically upgraded scenarios, which produce more interesting and useful assessment outcomes (Sailer et al., 2021). Different learning styles and preferences can be accommodated by using a variety of scenario-based assessment methods, such as written responses, oral presentations, simulations, and role-playing exercises. This also gives students many opportunities to demonstrate their comprehension and skills (Griffith, Wolfeld, Armon, Rios, & Liu, 2016). A thorough assessment of student performance is ensured by using a range of assessment techniques, which also helps to produce more accurate and insightful assessment findings (Haynes et al., 2009).

Factors Inhibiting Scenario-Based Assessment Results

Ensuring the efficacy of the educational system depends on restoring the quality of assessments, which is of utmost importance to all stakeholders in the educational process. Many scholars have contributed their observations about the challenges that other nations using competency-based curricula and scenario-based assessments have found impact the results of these types of evaluations. Uganda cannot stand out from the rest if these challenges are not recognized and overcome. These challenges are diverse in forms and are not restricted to the following;

Hodges et al, (2013) argued that ambiguous learning objectives are a major barrier to scenario-based assessment outcomes (Leung, Trevena, & Waters, 2016). Students may find it difficult to comprehend the goal of the assessment and to successfully demonstrate their knowledge and skills inside the scenario if the learning objectives are unclear or poorly specified. This calls for the extra mile roles of curriculum developers and educators to ensure that learning objectives are clear and achievable within a given period and teachers should equally offer more guidance for the learners (Hodge, Hugman, Varndell, & Howes, 2013).

Boud and Falchikov (2007), emphasize how item developers' bias has a significant impact on scenario-based assessment results in both formative and summative assessment situations. Examiner bias can distort the feedback given in formative assessments, which emphasize the importance of feedback for students' growth. This prevents students from identifying areas in which they need to improve. Similar to this, biases in evaluation might jeopardize the validity and fairness of assessment outcomes

in summative assessments, where decisions are made in comparison to predefined standards. The integrity and efficacy of scenario-based assessment outcomes depend on overcoming the bias of item developers, whether in formative or summative contexts (Bennett, Deane, & W. van Rijn, 2016). This calls for close consideration of assessment design, examiner training, and continuous quality assurance procedures (Boud, 2021). Inadequate feedback mechanisms, according to Sambell and McDowell (1998), impede the outcomes of scenario-based assessments as students might not be able to recognize their areas of strength and weakness, work on those areas, and improve their learning and performance on subsequent tests without prompt and helpful feedback (Authentic, Brown, & Sambell, 2023).

According to Van Berkel and Bax (2002), scenario-based assessment outcomes may be hampered by situations' insufficient authenticity (Purpura, 2021). In the event that scenarios fail to authentically reflect the real-world obstacles or circumstances, students can find it difficult to participate in the assessment tasks and exhibit their capacity to utilize their acquired knowledge and abilities in useful scenarios. Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick (2006) pointed out that outcomes from scenario-based assessments are hampered by an overemphasis on content coverage. Exams that place an emphasis on fact memorization or a superficial mastery of the material may prevent students from developing higher-order competences like critical thinking and problem-solving that are necessary for success in scenario-based exams (Heidari, 2024). Resource limitations may obstruct the outcomes of scenario-based assessments, as observed by Sailer et al., 2021 (Kastorff et al., 2023). Assessment results may be impacted if students do not have access to the tools, technology, equipment, or materials they need to participate completely in the evaluation process and display their talents as intended (Sailer et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The global shift towards Competency-Based Curricula (CBC) marks a significant revolution in education, particularly evident in Uganda, where traditional content-centric approaches are giving way to dynamic, student-centered models. As Uganda prepares its students for final summative assessments within this framework, scenario-based assessment emerges as a groundbreaking evaluation tool rooted in constructivist learning theories. Scholars have extensively explored various forms of scenario-based assessment, emphasizing its role in promoting active learning, critical thinking, and practical competence across diverse subjects and domains. Real-world scenarios integrated into assessment tasks enhance student engagement and relevance, fostering deeper learning and more accurate assessment outcomes. Structured rubrics provide transparent criteria for evaluating student performance, ensuring consistency and fairness in evaluation. Collaborative learning settings encourage peer interaction and discussion, exposing students to diverse perspectives and real-world challenges. Timely and constructive feedback guides student learning and reflection, promoting continuous improvement. However, several factors inhibit scenario-based assessment outcomes, including ambiguous learning objectives, item developers' bias, inadequate feedback mechanisms, insufficient authenticity of scenarios, overemphasis on content coverage, and resource limitations. Overcoming these obstacles requires careful attention to assessment design, examiner training, feedback mechanisms, and resource allocation. By addressing these challenges and leveraging facilitating factors, scenario-based assessment can play a pivotal role in empowering students with the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to succeed in the 21st century and beyond.

In conclusion, scenario-based assessment holds tremendous promise for transforming education and preparing students for the complexities of the modern world, but effective implementation requires a concerted effort to overcome inhibiting factors and optimize facilitating conditions.

Recommendation

The curriculum developers should make sure that the learning outcomes are well-defined and are in line with assessment criteria as teachers/educators also provide a pivotal strategies in adapting to the use of various instructional materials that can create realistic world scenarios within their subject areas for the students and assist them in creating scenario task items based on expected learning outcomes. This clarity directs examiners in appropriately assessing performance and aids students in understanding their expectations in order for them to structure their responses.

The preservation of fairness, validity, and reliability in the assessment process depends on providing scenario-task developers and teachers with training. It also supports their ongoing professional development and that of the students, who benefit from the ability to approach assessments with confidence, develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, participate in active learning experiences, collaborate with others effectively, reflect on their learning, and get ready for challenges in the future. Students who receive this thorough preparation perform better academically overall and are better prepared for success in their future pursuits.

In order to enhance fairness and reliability in assessment outcomes, there is a need to develop standardized rubrics in scenario-based assessment tools that specify precise criteria for evaluating student responses in a given subject or domain. These criteria should be transparent and applied consistently during item scores.

Use quality control methods to keep an eye on and assess how well scenario-based assessment techniques are working. This could involve frequent audits of the assessment procedures, continuous training sessions for item developers, feedback systems for ongoing improvement, and departmental or team development of scenario tasks and moderation before being administered to the students.

To identify areas for improvement and advancement in learning, teachers should encourage students to provide ongoing feedback and to reflect on their experiences with the scenario-based assessment methods as this feedback loop will contribute to modification of assessment strategies and student performance.

Make sure there are sufficient resources like technology, materials, and support staff available to support scenario-based assessment activities. This will help students become familiar with a variety of scenarios and help them create responses based on real-world circumstances or scenarios more quickly. Insufficient resources have the potential to impede student involvement and curtail the efficacy of evaluation results.

When developing scenarios and selecting scenario item developers, consider a range of perspectives and backgrounds to minimize bias and improve fairness in assessment outcomes. Adopt a culture of continuous improvement by periodically analyzing and improving scenario-based assessment methods in light of user input and the efficacy of data.

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Authors' Contributions

All authors had equal contributions to all stages of this study and all authors read and approved the first draft of the manuscript.

References

- Afandi, D. M. (2023). *The influence of using problem-based learning (PBL) method on the student's reading comprehension in descriptive text at the tenth-grade students of SMA Negeri 1 Sekampung East Lampung*. IAIN Metro.
- Aithal, P., & Mishra, N. (2024). Integrated framework for experiential learning: Approaches & impacts. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 8(1), 145-173.
- Al-Huneidi, A., & Schreurs, J. (2013). Constructivism based blended learning in higher education. In *Information Systems, E-learning, and Knowledge Management Research: 4th World Summit on the Knowledge Society, WSKS 2011, Mykonos, Greece, September 21-23, 2011* (Revised Selected Papers, Vol. 4). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-35879-1_29
- Authentic, C. M., Brown, S., & Sambell, U. K. (2023). *Rethinking assessment by formative and shared assessment to promote global university learning*.
- Bardach, L., Klassen, R. M., Durksen, T. L., Rushby, J. V., Bostwick, K. C., & Sheridan, L. (2021). The power of feedback and reflection: Testing an online scenario-based learning intervention for student teachers. *Computers & Education*, 169, Article 104194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104194>
- Barkley, E. F., Major, C. H., & Cross, K. P. (2014). *Collaborative learning techniques: A handbook for college faculty*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bennett, R. E., Deane, P., & van Rijn, P. W. (2016). From cognitive-domain theory to assessment practice. *Educational Psychologist*, 51(1), 82-107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2016.1115523>
- Berry, R. (2008). *Assessment for learning* (Vol. 1). Hong Kong University Press.
- Binti Pengiran, P. H. S. N., & Besar, H. (2018). Situated learning theory: The key to effective classroom teaching? *HONAI*, 1(1).
- Boud, D. (2021). Assessment-as-learning for the development of students' evaluative judgement. In *Assessment as Learning* (pp. 25-37). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003088498-3>

- Charles, K., Song, Z., & Khaing, T. (2022). Factors affecting the implementation of competency-based curriculum in lower secondary schools in Uganda: A systematic literature review.
- Clark, I. (2012). Formative assessment: Assessment is for self-regulated learning. *Educational Psychology Review*, 24, 205-249. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-011-9191-6>
- Darabi, A., Arrastia, M. C., Nelson, D. W., Cornille, T., & Liang, X. (2011). Cognitive presence in asynchronous online learning: A comparison of four discussion strategies. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 27(3), 216-227. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2010.00392.x>
- Demetriadis, S. N., Papadopoulos, P. M., Stamelos, I. G., & Fischer, F. (2008). The effect of scaffolding students' context-generating cognitive activity in technology-enhanced case-based learning. *Computers & Education*, 51(2), 939-954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2007.09.012>
- Dolmans, D., & Schmidt, H. (2010). The problem-based learning process. In *Lessons from Problem-Based Learning* (pp. 13-20). <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199583447.003.0003>
- Errington, E. P. (2010). Preparing graduates for the professions: Achieving employability through the exploration of near-world scenarios. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 5, 1-10.
- Griffith, R. L., Wolfeld, L., Armon, B. K., Rios, J., & Liu, O. L. (2016). Assessing intercultural competence in higher education: Existing research and future directions. *ETS Research Report Series*, 2016(2), 1-44. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ets2.12107>
- Guerrero-Roldán, A.-E., & Noguera, I. (2018). A model for aligning assessment with competences and learning activities in online courses. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 38, 36-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2018.04.005>
- Haynes, S. R., Spence, L., & Lenze, L. (2009). Scenario-based assessment of learning experiences. Paper presented at the 2009 39th IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FIE.2009.5350814>
- Heidari, A. (2024). Examining learner's evaluative judgment supported by technology-enabled feedback information.
- Hendry, G. D., Frommer, M., & Walker, R. A. (1999). Constructivism and problem-based learning. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 23(3), 369-371. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877990230307>
- Himmele, P., & Himmele, W. (2017). *Total participation techniques: Making every student an active learner*. ASCD.
- Hodge, A., Hugman, A., Varndell, W., & Howes, K. (2013). A review of the quality assurance processes for the Australasian Triage Scale (ATS) and implications for future practice. *Australasian Emergency Nursing Journal*, 16(1), 21-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aenj.2012.12.001>
- Hyun, J., Ediger, R., & Lee, D. (2017). Students' satisfaction on their learning process in active learning and traditional classrooms. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 29(1), 108-118.
- Kastorff, T., Sailer, M., Vejvoda, J., Schultz-Pernice, F., Hartmann, V., Hertl, A., ... & Stegmann, K. (2023). Context-specificity to reduce bias in self-assessments:

Comparing teachers' scenario-based self-assessment and objective assessment of technological knowledge. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 55(6), 917-930. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2022.2144964>

Kaweesi, M., Ayebare, J., Atibuni, D. Z., & Olema, D. K. (2023). Faculty's perspectives of/on cultural diversity management in a multicultural classroom: The case of a Ugandan university. *International Journal of African Higher Education*, 10(1), 50-77. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ahe.2023.005>

Kidega, C., Song, Z., Ugochinyere, I. C., James, O. A., & Ndikubwimana, F. (2024). Confronting challenges facing teachers in implementing competency-based curriculum in Uganda: A case of secondary schools in Gulu City. *East African Journal of Education Studies*, 7(2), 112-129.

King, D. (2012). New perspectives on context-based chemistry education: Using a dialectical sociocultural approach to view teaching and learning. *Studies in Science Education*, 48(1), 51-87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057267.2012.655037>

Klaassen, R. G. (2018). Interdisciplinary education: A case study. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 43(6), 842-859. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2018.1452865>

Krenik, J. (2014). *The influence of problem-based learning on drawing ability* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).

Lave, J. (1991). Situating learning in communities of practice.

Leung, K., Trevena, L., & Waters, D. (2016). Development of a competency framework for evidence-based practice in nursing. *Nurse Education Today*, 39, 189-196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2016.01.026>

Marshall, D. A., Burgos-Liz, L., IJzerman, M. J., Crown, W., Padula, W. V., Wong, P. K., ... & Osgood, N. D. (2015). Selecting a dynamic simulation modeling method for health care delivery research—Part 2: Report of the ISPOR dynamic simulation modeling emerging good practices task force. *Value in Health*, 18(2), 147-160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2015.01.006>

McAlpine, L., Weston, C., Beauchamp, C., Wiseman, C., & Beauchamp, J. (1999). Building a metacognitive model of reflection. *Higher Education*, 37, 105-131. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1003544129005>

Mirijamdotter, A., Somerville, M. M., & Holst, M. (2006). An interactive and iterative evaluation approach for creating collaborative learning environments. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems Evaluation*, 9(2), 83.

Murphy, E. (1997). Constructivism: From philosophy to practice.

Mutweleli, S., Mwathe, G., & Mundi, S. (2024). Scenario-based assessments: Experience from East Africa. In *The contextualisation of 21st century skills: Assessment in East Africa* (pp. 135-149). Springer.

Nicol, D. J., & Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006). Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: A model and seven principles of good feedback practice. *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(2), 199-218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070600572090>

Norris, M. B., Grohs, J. R., & Knight, D. B. (2022). Investigating student approaches to scenario-based assessments of systems thinking. Paper presented at the *Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)*.

- Palm, T. (2019). Performance assessment and authentic assessment: A conceptual analysis of the literature. *Practical Assessment, Research & Evaluation*, 13(1), 4.
- Pitchford, A., Owen, D., & Stevens, E. (2020). *A handbook for authentic learning in higher education: Transformational learning through real world experiences*. Routledge.
- Purpura, J. E. (2021). A rationale for using a scenario-based assessment to measure competency-based, situated second and foreign language proficiency.
- Renzulli, J. S., Gentry, M., & Reis, S. M. (2021). *Enrichment clusters: A practical plan for real-world, student-driven learning*. Routledge.
- Resnick, L. B., & Resnick, D. P. (1992). Assessing the thinking curriculum: New tools for educational reform. In *Changing assessments: Alternative views of aptitude, achievement, and instruction* (pp. 37-75). Springer.
- Sailer, M., Stadler, M., Schultz-Pernice, F., Franke, U., Schöffmann, C., Paniotova, V., ... & Fischer, F. (2021). Technology-related teaching skills and attitudes: Validation of a scenario-based self-assessment instrument for teachers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115, Article 106625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106625>
- Salend, S. J. (2010). *Creating inclusive classrooms*. Pearson Education.
- Schuwirth, L. W., & Van der Vleuten, C. P. (2003). The use of clinical simulations in assessment. *Medical Education*, 37, 65-71. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2923.37.s1.8.x>
- Segers, M., Dochy, F., & De Corte, E. (1999). Assessment practices and students' knowledge profiles in a problem-based curriculum. *Learning Environments Research*, 2, 191-213. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009911501134>
- Seren Smith, M., Warnes, S., & Vanhoestenbergh, A. (2018). Scenario-based learning. In *UCL IOE Press*.
- Singh, N. (2011). Student-centered learning (SCL) in classrooms—A comprehensive overview. *Educational Quest—An International Journal of Education and Applied Social Sciences*, 2(2), 275-282. <https://doi.org/10.5958/j.2230-7311.2.2.010>
- Smith, M. S., & Casserly, C. M. (2006). The promise of open educational resources. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 38(5), 8-17. <https://doi.org/10.3200/CHNG.38.5.8-17>
- Taras, M. (2016). Situating power potentials and dynamics of learners and tutors within self-assessment models. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 40(6), 846-863. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2015.1070409>
- Utley, R. (2010). *Theory and research for academic nurse educators: Application to practice*. Jones & Bartlett Publishers.
- Wenger, E. (2022). Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger. In *Understanding and using educational theories* (p. 257).
- Zhang, M., van Rijn, P. W., Deane, P., & Bennett, R. E. (2019). Scenario-based assessments in writing: An experimental study. *Educational Assessment*, 24(2), 73-90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10627197.2019.1615636>